

Speculation on Quantum Interaction Related Information Paired with Uncertainty

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We have argued in previous notes that free particle quantum mechanics, specifically the probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, emerges from the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ which is degenerate for $t=t_0+n\hbar/E$ and $x=x_0+n\hbar/p$ ($n=\text{integer}$). This, together with a $P_1(p_1x)P_1(p_2x)=P_1((p_1+p_2)x)$ leads to the form $\exp(ipx)$. We try to consider this in terms of information (a constraint) and an uncertain variable (the variables in the constraint $x'/t'=v$) and also consider the role played by a phase shift.

We try to examine the role of information in leading to quantum formalism. We first note that a very special kind of information is used together with the usual x,t , namely E and p . This follows from considering a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$, t from a frame moving with constant speed $-v$. The constraint $x'/t'=v$ leads to the forms of $E=m_0cc/\sqrt{(1-vv/cc)}$ and $p=m_0v/\sqrt{(1-vv/cc)}$. In other words, these important variables for quantum mechanics seem to be (a) linked to the rest frame and (b) linked to a constraint $x'/t'=v$ which is used to define the Lorentz matrix. We thus suggest that the rest frame should be examined more closely for other constraints to see if these have quantum mechanical consequences.

We first note that m_0 is constrained to be a point, i.e. to be localized in space. If p follows from a constraint $x'/t'=v$ and leads to uncertainty in x , then we suggest that there should be some uncertainty associated with the localization of m_0 , but in this case there is no variable like x to measure it. We further argue that p for a free particle can always be made to lie along one axis, suggesting a special axis, but there are actually three axes for m_0 in all cases. In other words, there may be some uncertainty in space associated with the localization of m_0 in space, but there is also the issue of the 3 axis together with the notion of a special axis for a given space. We also note that the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ formalism also follows directly from special relativity, i.e. The Lorentz invariant $-EE=pp+m_0m_0$ with $E= \partial/\partial t$ and $p= -i\text{grad}$.

We stress that the uncertainty associated with the localization of m_0 is not linked to a variable such as ϕ used for angular momentum because this localisation does not involve motion in ϕ due to a torque. Nevertheless, the localisation suggests an asymmetry in 3-space in much the same way that angular momentum is based on an asymmetry in 3-space, i.e. a spherical distribution has no angular momentum.

Quantum Mechanics from Special Relativity

We have argued in previous notes that the $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, quantum impulse probability (wavefunction), may be obtained from the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ because A is degenerate for $x=x_0+\hbar n/p$ and $t=t_0+n\hbar/E$, where $n=\text{integer}$. Using this notion of gradations in space and seeking a probability such that $P_1(p_1x)P_1(p_2x)=P_1((p_1+p_2)x)$ leads to $\exp(ipx)$ and then $\exp(-iEt)$ as solutions.

Here we wish to consider this from the point of view of a constraint leading to information. The first question is: What information should one use? We start with the simplest information, namely a rest mass at $x=0$ at t . When viewed from a moving frame, this particle has E and p

which arise naturally when one imposes the constraint $x'/t'=v$. In other words, one can create a 2x2 matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} A & vg(v) \\ B & g(v) \end{bmatrix} \quad ((1))$$

which transforms x, t to x', t' such that $x'/t'=v$. If this same matrix is applied to $(0, mocc)$, then it transforms to E, p . If one suggests that:

$$(0, mo) \text{ Matrix transpose } \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \text{ Matrix } (0) = (0, mo) \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ mo \end{bmatrix} \quad ((2))$$

Then one has: $EE = pp + momo$ ($c=1$). The -1 in the matrix between the transformation matrices ensures that $EE-pp$ can equal $momo$, because it is assumed that $E > mocc$ and $p > 0$. (Then $A=g(v)$ and $B=vg(v)$.)

Thus, E and p become the important variables emerging from special relativity and the constraint $x'/t'=v$. In other words, this constraint gives rise to these variables and so they are known information, i.e. fixed by a constraint and conserved (as long as there is no interaction). Interestingly, this known information following from a constraint, leads to uncertainty in the variables linked with the constraint, namely x, t . In particular, the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ is degenerate for $t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E$ and $x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p$. Thus uncertainty or probability in one variable is linked with certainty/known information or conservation in another. This may even be used quantitatively as in:

$$\int dx \exp(-ip_1'x - ip_2'x) \exp(ip_1x + ip_2x) = 0 \quad \text{if } p_1' + p_2' \neq p_1 + p_2 \quad ((3))$$

The uncertainty in one variable linked with a known variable leads to the idea of orthogonality. The uncertainty or probability is of a very special form, e.g. $\exp(-iEt)$ or $\exp(ipx)$ and not simply a random variable.

Given the form $\exp(ipx)$, one has a probability form in space linked with p . The physical significance of p , we argue, is that it is proportional to impulse, so one has a complex impulse probability. As a result, one may phase shift $\exp(ipx)$ to $\exp(ipx + i \text{ phase shift})$. This represents a different impulse pattern in x when compared to $\exp(ipx)$, even though both have the same wavelength. Obtaining a phase shift is associated with interactions associated with the notion of an impulse cycle. For example, p could change suddenly to p_1 (due to a sudden change from one constant potential V_1 to another, V_2 , changing the wavelength and the particle could move a distance L . If $p_1L = 2\pi \cdot 1.4$, nothing is noticed, but if a partial cycle occurs and the particle suddenly changes back to p , there is a phase shift. This can happen in various ways so a phase shift represents some information that an interaction occurred which did not allow a cycle to complete. This interaction is not like p or E , i.e. a conserved object and so in a sense only acts as a measure of whether a cycle was completed or not.

Spin

Given that the above arguments follow from constraints arising in special relativity and the transformation of a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at t (for the massive particle situation), one should examine this state, we suggest. The form $\exp(ipx) \exp(-iEt)$ follows from $A = -Et+px$ and so also holds for a photon, but a rest mass state does not, so there should be some other different quantum features of a photon (e.g. spin).

We suggest that constraint applying to a rest mass m_0 at a point $x=0$ at t should be strongly connected to free particle quantum mechanics if p leads to $\exp(-ipx)$ and E to $\exp(-iEt)$ because these follow from the constraint $x'/t'=v$ and viewing the rest mass from a frame moving with constant $-v$. It seems there are two constraint issues linked with a rest mass. First, it is a localized object in space and this, we argue, has important consequences because the angular momentum operator $r \times p$ with $p=-i \text{ grad}$ leads and $L \cdot L$ leads to $Y_{lm}(\theta, \phi)$ as an eigenfunction. This eigenfunction breaks spherical symmetry. In other words, spherical symmetry represents zero angular momentum. It is θ which breaks this symmetry, but this implies some kind of localization in space, even if r is infinite.

We suggest that localizing a particle with m_0 at $x=0$ (and $y=0, z=0$) also leads to localization of space and should be analogous to the angular momentum case. One might argue that one could have a spherical distribution about $(x=0, y=0, z=0)$, but we suggest that because p can always be made to lie along one axis, that even though one has 3 spatial axes, one always has a special axis. (One may note that this special axis only appears in special relativity when one observes a particle at rest from a moving frame (constant $-v$), but we also note that the Dirac approach to spin $\frac{1}{2}$ formalism arises from special relativity which considers p present.)

The special axis does not need to be in the direction of p , but just like p representing a state linked with one axis, one has a state due to localization linked with one axis (even though there are 3).

We argue that a localized m_0 with p emerging in one direction is akin to a localisation in angular space, (no spherical symmetry), but unlike angular momentum one does not have physical motion about ϕ (an axis) which completes when ϕ changes from $-$ to 2π . (For spin it is 0 to 4π). There is no physical rotation in the usual sense here. Rather there is some angular motion due to the localization of m_0 . This spin may be associated with a given axis and is quantized due to the localization of m_0 , but there are 3 axes and so there is no reason that a known spin projection on one axis means one knows about the other two axes. (Like a p state, spin (or spin projection) is linked with one axis.)

The main point we wish to stress is that the existence of spin $\frac{1}{2}$ is known from experiment and Dirac linearized a special relativity equation ($-\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} W = (-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} + m_0) W$ with $E=i\frac{d}{dt}$ partial and $p=-i\text{grad}$, in order to develop spin $\frac{1}{2}$ formalism. We wish to know why spin should exist in the first place. We suggest (speculate) that it is due to constraints of localization on m_0 because $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ follow from viewing m_0 (which is localized) from a moving frame with a different constraint applied, namely $x'/t'=v$. In other words, we try to argue that constraints lead to quantum probability, usually in a second variable like x or θ , ϕ . For spin, one does not have a frame from which creates the localization of m_0 , unlike the

case of a moving object (constant $-v$ frame) or a rotating object (rotating frame). Thus, spin is more complicated, but similar to rotation due to the similar localization properties, we speculate.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we speculate that free particle quantum mechanics seems to be linked with the variables E and p which arise from special relativity due to the constraint $x'/t'=v$. Thus, E and p are known and based on a constraint and so are conserved in a sense. This seems to lead to a specific kind of uncertainty in the variables which are part of the constraint, namely $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$. In fact, this specific probability ensures that E and p are conserved in the sense of $\int dx \exp(-ip_1'x-ip_2'x) \exp(ip_1x+ip_2x) = 0$ if $p_1'+p_2' \neq p_1+p_2$ ((3))

Uncertainty together with certainty allows one to have orthogonality. If this is really the case, then we argue that because E and p follow from observing a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$, t from a frame moving with constant $-v$, there should be some quantum significance of the localization of m_0 at $x=0$ ($y=0, z=0$) and the seemingly preferred axis arising from the direction of p . We argue that this constraint leads to the idea of spin which seems to be similar to angular momentum because both represent a localisation (non-spherical situation). Angular momentum, however, follows ϕ from 0 to 2π as a complete cycle while spin has 0 to 4π . With spin, one does not have physical rotation as in the case of angular momentum so there is no 2π complete cycle, we speculate.

In other words, we try to argue that if $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ follow from constraints which arise in special relativity (i.e. the constraint $x'/t'=v$) resulting from the moving frame, then the localisation of m_0 in the rest frame should give rise to a quantum notion and we speculate that this is spin. In other words, a known constraint in certain variables (space variables) leads to a certain result, a particle with m_0 at rest. Thus, the space variables should be linked with uncertainty and this suggests some kind of angular motion, but not a regular one as no torque has been applied, it is simply linked with a localization constraint, we speculate.